

Analysis of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills Through Solving Fraction Problems in 3rd Grade Students of SDN 4 Karangmalang

Fitriyah Amalia^{1*}, Taufiq Hanafi², Erlanda Dinda Lestari³, Sofiyani⁴, Aurelia Theysa Putri⁵

Universitas Muria Kudus

Corresponding Author: Fitriyah Amalia fitriyah.amaliyah@umk.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Mathematical Solving, Fractions, Learning Strategies

Received : 10, May

Revised : 13, June

Accepted: 24, July

©2023 Amalia, Hanafi, Lestari, Sofiyani, Putri. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe the mathematical solving of grade 3 elementary school fractions as a form of education. Education is the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and habits by a group of people, which are transmitted from one generation to the next through teaching, training or research. The research method used in this article is a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach. Sources of data come from scores of written test results and problem-solving abilities, documents, and interviews. The research instrument used was test questions to obtain data on students' mathematical problem-solving abilities. Data collection techniques carried out by researchers were written tests, documentation, and interviews. Based on the results of the study it was concluded that the results of this analysis can be a reference for teachers and schools to identify areas of student weakness and design appropriate learning strategies to improve their mathematical problem-solving abilities.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and habits by a group of people, transmitted from one generation to the next through teaching, training, or research. Training is often done under the guidance of others, but it is also possible to be self-taught. Education is one of the important things that become the focus of a country's attention, and the Indonesian government is no exception. At every level of education, there must be math learning. Math learning in schools starts gradually from elementary school to college level. Different basic concepts are basically given in elementary school. Therefore, elementary school math is important. Elementary schools are expected to teach problem-solving skills and be able to develop students' ability to solve problems until higher levels of education.

In every level of education, mathematics must be learned. (Susanto, 2013) states that mathematics is one of the fields that can improve thinking and argumentation skills, help in solving daily problems and the world of work, and help in the development of science and technology. Mathematics is a subject that students learn and helps them acquire problem-solving skills. According to (Mairing, 2018) Mathematics is one of the subjects that encourage students' problem-solving skills, the ability to solve problems requires the ability to think logically when solving problems.

In learning mathematics, how the learning process is carried out will affect how well students learn the material. (Sundayana, 2014) states that the implementation of learning is the most determining factor in achieving educational goals. Mathematics learning includes systematic, logical, and critical thinking. Problem-solving is one of the modern skills that need to be developed through mathematics learning. The purpose of mathematics learning is for students to understand mathematical problems, understand the problem, identify and ask mathematical questions, and analyze the answers, and find a logical structure to face mathematical challenges. Learning carried out in mathematics material needs to be carried out along with the problem-solving skills possessed.

Problem-solving is one of the skills in learning mathematics. This is because the process of solving math problems makes it easier for students to solve problems systematically. Therefore, students will later gain experience in the field and skills to solve problems that are usually elementary students' problems in the form of problem-solving. Therefore, by studying mathematics, students can solve deep problems in everyday life such as counting and others. Problem-solving skills are needed in learning mathematics. According to Prabawanto in the article (Delyana, 2015) states that the ability to solve problems is the main competency that must be achieved in learning

mathematics. This is as mentioned in the education curriculum in Indonesia. (Phanopichat, June 2023) the article (Tandri Aisah, Dina Anika Marhayani, 2022) explains that this problem-solving ability is needed by students in everyday life. However, most students have weaknesses in problem-solving.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Problem-solving also means finding ways out of problems to achieve difficult goals. In mathematics learning, problem-solving should be seen as a process where a person is exposed to mathematical concepts, skills, and processes to solve mathematical problems.

As shown by (Mahmudah, 2018) and (Kodariyati, 2016) research on problem-solving ability using Newman's theory has also been conducted. They argue that the two main factors that usually cause student failure are their lack of reasoning ability and creativity in solving problems in real contexts and converting them into algebra. Likewise, using Polya and Nctm indicators says that students are not used to using the problem solving process correctly, which is the most significant factor. (Oktaviana, 2017) also conducted research using Newman's theory. The purpose of the study was to evaluate errors made by students in discrete courses using Newman's theory. (P., 2019) also conducted another study, according to the results, the subjects made different errors according to their abilities, but the most frequent error was writing the final answer by 70%. Similar research has also been conducted (Kania, 2019), many of which amounted to 33.33% of final answer writing errors.

In fact, in elementary schools, math lessons that develop problem-solving skills have not been taught to students. This is because teachers have not developed these skills in math lessons, which results in students lacking problem-solving skills according to Mulyati (Delyana, 2015) So, to solve mathematical problems the steps taken are as follows: (a) understanding the problem; (b) devising a plan; (c) carrying out the plan; and (d) looking back. By considering the previous situation, therefore, research on the ability to solve problems referred to as "Analysis of the Ability to Solve Mathematical Problems through solving Fraction Material problems in Grade 3 Elementary Schools at SDN 4 Karang Malang". This research is very important because the aim is to identify the ability of students in fraction material in grade 3 elementary school. In addition, they want to find out where the learners' mistakes are and tell teachers how to use effective teaching strategies to deal with this problem. It is hoped that this research will provide a basis for teachers to help create an effective learner-learning atmosphere.

METHODOLOGY

This section contains the research design including research design, research population/sample, data collection techniques and instruments, data analysis tools, and research models used. The research method used in this article is a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach. According to (Soegiyono, 2011) the qualitative descriptive analysis method aims to describe, describe as a whole and in depth about the occurrence of various phenomena studied thoroughly, broadly, and deeply. This research was conducted in 1 elementary school in Kudus City with the subject of third grade students consisting of 12 students. In the elementary school, students with high ability (KT), medium ability (KS), and low ability (KR) were selected. The data used in this study consisted of 1) data on mathematical problem solving ability at each ability level. The data source comes from the written test scores of problem solving ability and, documents, and interviews. The research instrument used was a test question to obtain data on students' mathematical problem solving ability. The data collection techniques carried out by researchers are written tests, documentation, and interviews.

The first research indicator: according to (Roebiyanto, 2017) in research (Setiawan & Dores, 2019) indicators of solving mathematical problems, namely: (1) Students can identify known elements, what is asked, and the sufficiency of the required elements, (2) Students can formulate mathematical problems or compile mathematical models, (3) re-examine the results of the solution. The second research: according to Polya in research (Oktavia et al., 2021) the indicators of mathematical problem solving are, : (1) understanding the given problem, (2) developing a solution plan from the problem, (3) implementing the solution plan, and (4) checking again. The third research: according to NCTM in research (Delyana, 2015) can summarize the indicators of mathematical problem solving ability, namely: 1. Understanding the problem at this stage, 2. Making a Plan to Solve the Problem, 3. Implementing Problem Solving, 4. Rechecking the Answers Obtained.

Thus, based on the research references above, we can conclude that the indicators of problem-solving ability are as follows: 1. Building new mathematical knowledge through problem-solving, 2. Applying and adjusting appropriate strategies to solve problems, 3. Solving problems and implementing solution plans that arise in mathematics, 4. Monitoring and re-examining mathematical problem-solving. According to (Newman, 1977) there are five types of errors, namely errors in reading the problem, errors in understanding the problem, errors in problem transformation, errors in the calculation process, and errors in writing the final answer. The purpose of this

study is to see how students' mathematical problem-solving skills on fraction material in student learning interest in the class.

RESULTS

The following is a description of the results of each student's answers from research conducted in class 3 SDN 04 Karangmalang Kudus in answering problem-solving questions about fractions. Based on the results of the tests carried out, many students had difficulty working. These difficulties can be known based on observation, interviews, and tests given by the researcher. Based on observations, interviews and tests, students have difficulty understanding concepts, difficulty solving problems, and difficulty working on problems.

Figure1. The Work of Respondent S-1 Has Difficulty in Understanding the Concept

Based on the picture above, students have difficulty in understanding the concepts in the questions given. Students still have difficulty distinguishing denominators and numerators and have difficulty distinguishing symbols less than and more than in fraction material. Understanding the concept of fractions is done by many students (Lestari et al., 2020).

1. Perhatikan Gambar di bawah ini!

Aurel membagi persegi panjang menjadi enam kotak.
Setiap kotak bernilai dua per enam.

Tentukan pembilang dan penyebut dari kotak tersebut...?
2/6 pembilang
6 penyebut

2. Bu Dina berbelanja di pasar, beliau membeli $\frac{1}{4}$ kg bawang merah, $\frac{1}{4}$ kg bawang putih, $\frac{1}{2}$ kg telur dan $\frac{1}{2}$ kg minyak goreng. Berat seluruh belanjaan Bu Dina adalah $\frac{10}{9}$ kg?

3. Pak Anang mempunyai 100 ekor bebek. Karena terkena penyakit, 6 ekor bebeknya mati. Kejadian itu hampir sama dengan bulan lalu. Bulan lalu 9 dari 100 ekor bebeknya mati karena dimangsa oleh musang. Nyatakan dalam bentuk pecahan, kemudian bandingkanlah pecahan tersebut!
 $\frac{6}{100} < \frac{9}{100}$

4. Sofi mempunyai $2\frac{1}{5}$ karung manga, setiap karung beratnya $12\frac{1}{2}$ kg. Berapa berat manga Sofi seluruhnya...? kg

Figure 2. The Results of the Work of Respondents S-2 Difficulty in Problem Solving

Based on the picture above, students have difficulty in solving the problems in the problems given by the researcher. Learners do not write about known, asked or answered and immediately choose to answer the questions given by the researcher. And the answers given are still wrong many are wrong. Learners immediately write the answers on the question sheet that has been given by the researcher (Lestari et al., 2020).

Figure 3. The Results of S-3's Response Work Have Difficulty in Understanding the Problem

Based on the picture above, students have difficulty understanding the problem so that students cannot solve the problems given by the researcher. Difficulty understanding the problem can be caused by a lack of understanding of the concept and also a lack of understanding of problem solving in the problem. In the question, the students only wrote answers that were not correct and there were also those who had not filled it in, (Lestari et al., 2020).

DISCUSSION

According to (Newman, 1977) there are five types of errors, namely errors in reading the problem, errors in understanding the problem, errors in problem transformation, errors in the calculation process, and errors in writing the final answer of the five errors found in this study. From the results of this study it can be found that S-1 had difficulty in understanding the concept of the problem given by the researcher. S-2 had difficulty in problem solving the problems given by the researcher. S-3 had difficulty in understanding the problems given by the researcher.

According to Newman, the first mistake students make is reading the problem. The results showed that according to this study, students did not experience difficulties in reading the problem because they had mastered their ability to read the problem repeatedly in grade 3, so only 3 to 4 students made mistakes in reading problems related to fraction material in grade 3 elementary school. The results of this study are similar to the results of research (Mahmudah, 2018), which shows that students have little difficulty in the reading part of the problem, but they have difficulty in understanding which part of the problem.

The second error was misunderstanding the problem, which accounted for 20% of the study. Some of these errors were not writing down what was known and what was asked. Learners could not read the important information in the problem because they could not understand each sentence, so they could not write it down. Not being used to working on story problems causes learners to not understand how to write what they know and what is asked in the problem. The results of this study support (Fatahillah, 2017) that students often do not write down what they know when they are asked or answered.

Learners usually say that they are not careful when working on problems. However, from the results of interviews and their work, it appears that they do not understand the problems and cannot convert them into mathematical

sentences, especially those related to the multiplication and division operations of fractions. This is in accordance with research findings by (Ramdhantri, 2018) and (Sari, 2018) which show that students make mistakes at the problem transformation stage because they do not understand how to convert sentences into mathematical form. In addition, difficulties in calculations can also occur because students do not understand the problem and also students who do not understand the concept. The mistake that students often make is incorrectly operating the two fractions. And this is in accordance with the findings in research by (Dyah Vitta Putri Lestari, et al 2021).

Most learners in the transformation error category faced difficulties in determining the fraction operation that should be used to solve the problem, which accounted for 16% of the total transformation errors. Learners observed said that factors leading to transformation errors included their lack of understanding of the meaning of the sentences involved in the problem, lack of attention required to solve the problem, and lack of accuracy when solving it.

Problem-solving difficulties usually occur when learners still have difficulty in understanding the concepts in a calculation. Learners who do not understand the concept of a problem or material must be wrong in calculating so this can cause students to have difficulty in solving the problems given. From the results that have been given by researchers, it shows that students who have difficulty in concepts will have difficulty in calculating so that problem solving on the overall answer of students will be wrong. Of all the problems given, it was found that students did not fully understand the problem. The lack of understanding is due to students not understanding the concept of the previous material perfectly and resulting in students being confused in answering questions so that they answer questions carelessly which makes their answers wrong (Tandri Aisah, Dina Anika Marhayani, 2022).

Calculation process difficulty is when learners have been able to determine the order of calculation operations of a problem but do not know the method needed to carry out the operation correctly. The mistake that learners make is not being able to do the calculation. The factor causing the difficulty of the calculation process is not understanding the material in depth so that it cannot mention and know the steps that will be used to solve the problem. According to (Sari, 2018) which reveals that students experience many difficulties in the calculation process because they do not fully understand the meaning of the question sentence.

The type of error that occurs when students cannot write the final result in the form of a sentence is the error in writing the final answer. Determination of answer writing errors is adjusted to Newman's error indicators, namely

students cannot make conclusions from the answers that have been completed. The most frequent error made by students is writing the final answer 3-4 times on each problem from one student who works on 4 available problems. With a percentage of 80%, based on the test results and student observations, it is considered that students have completed the task and have received the results before writing the final answer. In simple terms, the required writing of the final answer is to write the conclusion sentence that results from each question that answers it. However, students often do not do so. A study conducted by (Sari, 2018) found that the most frequent error made by students is this type.

The analysis of mathematical problem-solving ability through solving fraction problems for grade 3 students of SDN 4 Karangmalang can be done by looking at several factors including student's understanding of the concept of fractions, the ability to apply concepts in problem-solving situations, and the level of success of students in solving fraction problems. First, in this analysis, it is necessary to evaluate students' understanding of the concept of fractions. It can be done through giving tests or assignments to measure the extent to which students understand the basic concepts of fractions such as understanding fractions, calculating fractions, and operating with fractions. The results of this test will provide an overview of the extent to which students understand the concept of fractions.

Furthermore, students' ability to apply fraction concepts in problem-solving situations needs to be analyzed. This can be done by giving a series of problem solving problems involving fractions. These problems should require an understanding of the concept of fractions as well as the ability to apply the concept to solve problems. By seeing the extent to which students are able to apply the concept of fractions in problem solving, students' mathematical problem solving ability can be evaluated.

Finally, students' success rate in solving fraction problems also needs to be analyzed. This can be done by looking at the percentage of students who successfully solve fraction problems correctly. This can give an idea of how well students apply their knowledge and skills in solving mathematical problems involving fractions. During this analysis, it is also important to pay attention to other factors that can affect students' mathematical problem solving ability, such as the teaching methods used by teachers, the level of motivation of students, and the support provided by schools and families.

By analyzing the mathematical problem solving skills of grade 3 students of SDN 4 Karangmalang through solving fraction problems, a better understanding of the students' mastery of fraction concepts and their ability to apply them in problem solving can be obtained. The results of this analysis can

serve as a reference for teachers and schools to identify students' areas of weakness and design appropriate learning strategies to improve their mathematical problem solving skills.

CONCLUSIONS

Education is the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and habits by a group of people, transmitted from one generation to the next through teaching, training, or research. The analysis of mathematical problem solving ability through solving fraction problems in grade 3 students of SDN 4 Karangmalang can be done by looking at several factors which include students' understanding of the concept of fractions, the ability to apply concepts in problem solving situations, and the level of success of students in solving fraction problems.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so that research still needs to be done on the following titles "Analysis of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills Through Solving Fraction Problems in 3rd Grade Students of SDN 4 Karangmalang."

REFERENCES

- Delyana, H. (2015). Peningkatan Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematika Siswa Kelas VII Melalui Penerapan Pendekatan Open Ended. *Lemma*, 2(1),26–34. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.22202/jl.2015.v2i1.523>
- Fatahillah, A. W. (2017). Analisis Kesalahan Siswa dalam Menyelesaikan Soal Cerita Matematika Berdasarkan Tahapan Newman Beserta Bentuk Scaffolding yang Diberikan. . *Kadikma*, 8(1), 40-51.
- Kania, N. &. (2019). Analisis Kesulitan Calon Guru Sekolah Dasar Dalam Menyelesaikan Soal Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Berdasarkan Prosedur Newman. *Supremum Journal of Mathematics Education*, 3(1), 57-66., doi: 10.31235/osf.io/brwgs.
- Kodariyati, L. &. (2016). Pengaruh Modul PBL Terhadap Kemampuan Komunikasi Dan Pemecahan Masalah Matematika Peserta Didik Kelas V SD. . *Jurnal Prima Edukasia*, 4(1), 93-106. , doi:10.21831/jpe.v4i1.7713 (diakses pada tanggal 19 Juni 2023).
- Lestari, V. P., Saputro, B. A., & Sukamto, S. (2020). Analisis Kemampuan Memecahkan Masalah Matematika Materi Debit Pada Kelas V Sekolah Dasar. *EduBasic Journal: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar*, 2(2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ebj.v2i2.27211>
- Mahmudah, W. (2018). Analisis Kesalahan Siswa Dalam Menyelesaikan Soal Matematika Bertipe Hots Berdasar Teori Newman. . *Unisda Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 4(1), 49-56.

- Mairing, J. P. (2018). Penyelesaian Masalah Matematika Berakhir Terbuka Pada Siswa SMA. *Fibonacci: Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika dan Matematika*, 4(1), 61-70, doi.org/10.24853/fbc.4.1.61-70.
- Mursidik, E. M. (2014). Analisis Kemampuan Berpikir Kreatif Peserta Didik Dalam Memecahkan Masalah Matematika Open Ended Ditinjau Dari Tingkat Kemampuan Matematika. . *Jurnal Penelitian LPPM IKIP PGRI Madiun*, 2(1), 7-13. , (diakses pada tanggal 13 Oktober 2019 dari <http://ejournal.unipma.ac.id/index.php/JPLPPM/artikel/view/344>).
- Newman, M. A. (1977). *An analysis of sixth grade pupils' errors on written mathematical tasks*. Victorian Institute for Educational Research Bulletin, 39, 31-43.
- Oktavia, J., Safitri, R. D., & Utami, A. D. (2021). Analisis Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Siswa SD Berdasarkan Teori Polya. *Journal of Techonolgy Mathematics and Social Science*, 1(1), 14-21.
- Oktaviana, D. (2017). Analisis Tipe Kesalahan Berdasarkan Teori Newman Dalam Menyelesaikan Soal Cerita Pada Mata Kuliah Matematika Diskrit. *Edu Sains: Jurnal Pendidikan Sains & Matematika*, 5(2), 22-32. , doi.org/10.23971/eds.v5i2.719 .
- P., D. B. (2019). Analisis Kesalahan Mahasiswa dalam Menyelesaikan Soal Sistem Persamaan Non-Linear Berdasarkan Teori Newman. . *Proseding Sendika*, 5(1),67-71., <http://eproceedings.umpwr.ac.id/index.php/sendika/article/view/639/541>.
- Phanopichat, P. W. (Juni, 2023). An Analysis Of Elementary School Students' Difficulties In Mathematical Problem Solving. *Procedia Sosial and Science Journal*, 10.1016/J.Spspro.2014.01.728 .
- Ramdhantri, I. A. (2018). Error Analysis Of Students In Grade VI Of Bumirejo Elementary School 1 In Completing Flowchart Debit Story Problem. *Social, Humanities, and Educational Studies (SHEs): Conference Series*, 1(2), 208-216., doi.org/10.20962/shes.v1i2.26854. (diakses pada tanggal 17 Juni 2023).
- Roebyanto, G. &. (2017). *Pemecahan Masalah Matematika untuk PGSD*. . Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya. .
- Sari, R. M. (2018). Pengembangan Media Komik Matematika Materi Debit pada Siswa Kelas V Sekolah Dasar. Skripsi. Malang: Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar. *Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan. University of Muhammadiyah Malang*. Diakses pada tanggal 16 Juni 2023.
- Sundayana. (2014). *Media dan Alat Peraga dalam Pembelajaran Matematika*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Susanto, A. (2013). *Teori Belajar dan Pembelajaran Di Sekolah Dasar*. Jakarta: Prenada Media Group.

Setiawan, B., & Dores, O. J. (2019). Analisis Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Dan Penalaran Matematis Siswa Sekolah Dasar Se-Kota Sintang. *VOX EDUKASI: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan*, 10(2), 137-143. <https://doi.org/10.31932/ve.v10i2.565>

Soegiyono. (2011). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*.

Tandri Aisah, Dina Anika Marhayani, E. C. H. (2022). Analisis Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Siswa Ditinjau dari Minat Belajar di SD". *JURNAL GENTALA PENDIDIKAN DASAR Vol.7 No. 1 Juni 2022, Halaman 1-15 P-ISSN: 2614-7092, E-ISSN: 2621-9611, 7(I), 1-15*. <http://online-jurnal.unja.ac.id/index.php/gentala>